

THE VALUE OF THE RETINA AND THE DISTINCTIVE SIDES OF THE RETINA IN CHILDREN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6367559>

Kamolakhon Isaeva

Pediatric Faculty Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

The eyes are a paired organ, the work of which provides complete information about the world around us. This analyzer has a rather complex anatomy. Its important feature is binocular vision, which allows you to perceive the world around you with both eyes. The visual apparatus is highly sensitive to various harmful factors and needs especially careful care. The organs of vision are spherical in shape, which is why they are called "eyeballs". They are located in the recesses of the skull (eye sockets). The anterior surface of each eye is protected by the upper and lower eyelids. The main elements of the eyeball: cornea; iris; pupil; lens; retina; vitreous body; sclera.

The retina is a thin layer of nervous tissue located on the inside of the back of the eyeball. The retina is responsible for perceiving the image that is projected onto it with the help of the cornea and lens, and converts it into nerve impulses, which are then transmitted to the brain. The retina is most firmly connected with the underlying membranes of the eyeball along the edge of the optic nerve head. The thickness of the retina in different parts is not the same: at the edge of the optic disc it is 0.4–0.5 mm, in the central fossa 0.2–0.25 mm, in the fovea only 0.07–0.08 mm, in the region of the dentate lines about 0.1 mm. The most complex structure allows the retina to be the first to perceive light, process and transform light energy into irritation - a signal that encodes all the information about what the eye sees. The retina is a rather complex structure. Microscopically, there are 10 layers in the retina, counted from outside to inside. The main layers are the pigment epithelium and light-sensitive cells (photoreceptors). Then comes the outer limiting membrane, the outer nuclear layer, the outer reticular (synaptic) layer, the inner nuclear layer, the inner reticular layer, the ganglionic layer, the layer of nerve fibers, the inner boundary membrane. The pigment epithelium extends throughout the optic part of the retina and directly borders the underlying choroid, having a connection with the vitreous plate. Cone-like and rod-like cells, or more simply, rods and cones, got this name because of the shape of the outer segment. This type of cell is considered the first neuron of the retina. The sticks are regular cylindrical formations with a

length of 40 to 50 microns. The total number of rods in the entire retina is about 130 million. They provide vision in low light, such as at night, and have a very high light sensitivity. There are 7 million cones in the retina of the human eye and they only work in bright light conditions. They are responsible for central shaped vision and color perception.

The normal functioning of the child's visual system is a necessary condition for ensuring the visual process itself, for the development of all organs and systems of the body. The eye is not only an organ of vision, but also a "consumer" of light energy. Due to the stimulating effect of light in the body, the endocrine glands produce hormones of the pituitary, adrenal, thyroid, gonads, etc. A faster adaptation of the newborn's body to external conditions, its proper development and growth to a large extent depend on the correct functioning of the visual system. That is why the visual analyzer in children is formed quite quickly. The growth and development of the eye in a child is generally completed by the age of 2–3 years, and in the next 15–20 years there are fewer changes than in the first years. Especially important for the further normal functioning of the child's visual system is the correct laying and development of the organ of vision even before birth. There are special critical periods of development when the anlage of a particular organ becomes particularly sensitive to various damaging factors. The results of clinical observations indicate that disorders in the development of the eye can be caused by:

- avitaminosis A (blindness);
- influence of lithium chloride (cyclopia, anophthalmos) and sodium thiocyanate (hydrophthalmos);
- hypoxia (cataract, underdevelopment);
- diagnostic radiography of pregnant women (microphthalmos, cataract, blindness);
- infectious diseases, excessive or prolonged administration of drugs for diabetes mellitus (optic nerve aplasia, blindness, cataracts).

The retina is the most important component of the visual analyzer, which is its peripheral link. The most complex structure allows the retina to be the first to perceive light, process and transform light energy into a nerve impulse, which is then transmitted along a chain of neurons to the visual centers of the cerebral cortex, where visual information is perceived and processed. The retina is the inner membrane of the eyeball that lines the fundus of the eye. The most important place in the retina is the so-called yellow spot (macula) with a central (0.075 mm) area (fovea centralis). This area is the best perception of visual sensations. Children retina consists of 10 layers:

- pigment epithelium;
- layer of rods and cones;
- outer boundary membrane;
- outer nuclear layer;
- outer plexiform (mesh) layer;
- inner nuclear layer;
- inner plexiform layer;
- layer of ganglionic and multipolar cells;
- a layer of nerve fibers;
- internal boundary membrane.

The first four layers belong to the light-sensitive apparatus of the retina, and the rest make up the medulla. After the first half of the year and as the eyes grow, not only the outer, but also the inner layers of the retina stretch and become thinner. In this regard, the retina undergoes significant changes in the macular and especially the foveolar (central) region: only the 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 10th layers remain here, which ensures the future high resolution visual capacity of this zone.

REFERENCES:

1. Wadhvani M, Vashist P, Singh SS, Gupta V, Gupta N, Saxena R. Prevalence and causes of childhood blindness in India: A systematic review. *Indian J Ophthalmol.* 2020;
2. Gilbert C, Foster A. Childhood blindness in the context of VISION 2020--The right to sight. *Bull World Health Organ.* 2001;
3. Agarwal K, Balakrishnan D, Rani PK, Jalali S. Changing patterns of early childhood blinding conditions presenting to a tertiary eye center: The epidemic of retinopathy of prematurity in India. *Indian J Ophthalmol.* 2019

